

Australian Research Data Commons

PIDs Capability & Maturity Model for Institutions

Australian National Persistent Identifier Strategy

Developed by the Institutions Stakeholder Action Group

16/12/2025 v1.0

[doi:10.5281/zenodo.18383425](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18383425)

CONTENTS

Preamble and Audience	2
Acknowledgements	2
Introduction to PID Maturity	3
Benefits Realisation	4
Executive Champions or Sponsors	4
Policy	5
Responsibility	5
Resourcing	6
User Experience	6
RAiD Capability Maturity	7
Capability Maturity Matrix	8
Important References	14

Preamble and Audience

This document, the PIDs Capability & Maturity Model, has been developed and reviewed by members of the Institutions Stakeholder Action Group of the [Australian National Persistent Identifier \(PID\) Strategy](#). It is intended for organisational planning, program managers, and those tasked with leading PID policy, advocacy, implementation, and support. The capability maturity model aids organisations in assessing existing organisational maturity, in prioritising good foundations, and advises on essential resources and support. The model also provides a more systemic organisational overview of the target state that might be achieved, the range of areas and capabilities involved, and benefits that can be realised in a range of areas. This first half of this document includes important introductory discussion topics, which leads into the second half that lays out a capability maturity matrix. As a stakeholder community shared and developed resource, this document is expected to evolve with the national strategy and stakeholders' progress.

The capability maturity matrix below is designed to complement a number of other resources. The first resource is the [PID Value Proposition Resource](#) which outlines a number of value proposition scenarios for institutions. This is an introduction to the PID ecosystem, it provides high-level guidance on determining the context dependent value proposition for implementing PIDs in an institution, and suggests business functions that can be more PID enabled. The second resource is the [PIDs Implementation Guide](#) which includes “recipes” for a number of PID enabled areas that collate advice and recommendations for each area. For more detailed advice on implementing specific activities found within the capability maturity matrix, be sure to read the [PIDs Implementation Guide](#).

Acknowledgements

1st Working Group:

Rubbiya Ali, University of Queensland. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3241-5692>

Melroy Almeida, Australian Access Federation. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3522-7849>

Vanessa Crosby, CSIRO. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9474-6553>

Penny Cross, University of Wollongong. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3963-2107>

Michelle Duryea, Edith Cowan University. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9514-6499>

Michael Feeney, University of Queensland. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4944-381X>

Philippa Frame, Queensland University of Technology. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5191-0763>

Graham Galloway, University of Queensland. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0805-2775>

Siobhann McCafferty, ARDC. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2491-0995>

Linda O'Brien, Griffith University. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1477-8652>

Blanca Pizzani, University of the Sunshine Coast. <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9886-6027>

Rhiannon Rasins, Macquarie University. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1828-3443>

Sharron Stapleton, Griffith University. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6017-4211>

Alexis Tindall, Adelaide University. (co-chair) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1888-6693>

Tania Wilmann, James Cook University. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9048-6395>

Lyle Winton, ARDC. (co-chair) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3049-1221>

2nd Working Group:

Melroy Almeida, Australian Access Federation. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3522-7849>

Matthias Liffers, ARDC. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3639-2080>

Siobhann McCafferty, ARDC. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2491-0995>

Natasha Simons, ARDC. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0635-1998>

Alexis Tindall, University of Adelaide. (co-chair) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1888-6693>

Lyle Winton, ARDC. (co-chair) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3049-1221>

Scope, initial input, review and feedback were provided by members of the [Institutions Stakeholder Advisory Group](#) of the Australian National Persistence Identifier Strategy.

Introduction to PID Maturity

The systemic benefits of PIDs are well-documented in the [Incentives to Invest in Identifiers](#) report, published in 2023, and the National PID Strategy coordinates Australia's efforts to fully leverage these. The benefits include improved research quality, efficiency, reproducibility, and attribution, while reducing burden, and enhancing our understanding of research impact and capabilities. But in recognising the strategic value of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), it's vital to grasp the connection between institutional and sector-wide maturity. Institutional PID adoption strengthens the entire research ecosystem, and a mature ecosystem amplifies the benefits for each institution. This synergy underpins the Australian National PID Strategy that prioritises the adoption of key PIDs (ORCID, ROR, DOI, RAiD, and IGSN) in order to leverage these network effects. The objective of the maturity model is to map clear institutional pathways and national strategy consistent pathways that allows all institutions to benefit from institutional maturity, the national roadmap, and sector-wide maturity.

It is also important to consider PID implementation within the context of an organisation's broader data and information management maturity. PID adoption plays an important enabling role in organisational data strategies and data maturity uplift. At the same time, mature data governance frameworks and technical capabilities are required to embed PIDs effectively and maximise organisational benefits.

After feedback and discussion three general levels of maturity have been decided upon for the capability maturity matrix, each representing changes in institutional focus. **At a beginner level**, institutions will be focusing on...

- Purpose, policy and responsibility
- Clear communications and messaging regarding PIDs
- Establishing the ability to facilitate the creation or capture of PIDs

At an intermediate level, institutions will be focusing on...

- Actively using and linking PIDs within core systems
- Information flows, that are automatic and streamlined, and between appropriate environments (information flows to create PIDs, information flows from existing PIDs)
- PIDs being actively used to reduce re-keying efforts and to obtain information from trusted sources

- PIDs being externally visible to people and machines (via API)

And at an advanced level, institutions will focus on...

- Spending less time collecting and registering PID information, and time now better spent on using the information
- Using PID enabled information for reporting, insights and business intelligent, and decision making
- PIDs being used to identify impact, research to celebrate and showcase outcomes

This approach to maturity levels may differ from other capability maturity models in a few ways. The capability maturity matrix was intended to enable action, support action plan development, and guide an organisation's focus on essential activities, capabilities and benefits, rather than setting measures or indicators. As such the matrix does not have a level 1 or level 0 which might typically describe what is not being done well. Instead each level describes the activities and capabilities that an organisation will be establishing, recognising that most organisations will be beginning to plan more holistically for PIDs, and that capabilities may not necessarily follow a linear path.

Benefits Realisation

An important requirement in the development of the capability maturity matrix has been to ensure institutions begin to see benefits at all levels of maturity and increasingly with each stage of maturity. The benefits that are outlined within the matrix have also been listed here:

- Improved visibility and acknowledgement of your researchers, their outcomes, and their institutions.
- More complete, accurate, up-to-date and verified administrative information.
- Reduced administrative and reporting effort for staff and researchers, particularly in time spent re-entering data, correcting manual data entry, and re-validating information.
- More accurate and streamlined reporting for meeting external requirements, for internal evaluation, and for strategic analysis.
- Improved and clarified research information governance.
- Leveraging national forums and services for up-skilling, implementation, support and knowledge transfer.

Executive Champions or Sponsors

Strong executive-level endorsement can be a powerful foundational aid to implementing and maturing an institution's approach to PIDs. Effective and widespread adoption can depend on cultural change, or shifts in organisational approach, such as integration within existing tools and services, or allocation of resources. When present from an early stage, support from research leadership or directors can accelerate implementation and maturity. In some contexts, this may not occur first, and developing sponsorship may be an element of maturity over time.

Whenever it is generated, executive-level sponsorship signals that PID initiatives are a strategic priority for the institution, helping to clarify importance and objectives across all levels of the organisation.

Engaging with key executive-levels early in the process is crucial for fostering awareness of the initiative, garnering their active support, and ensuring an understanding of the potential benefits.

Obtaining sponsorship is not merely about endorsement, it plays a vital role in securing necessary resources and institutional commitment for PID-related improvements. Articulating the value proposition of enhanced PID maturity, including its contribution to risk management, competitiveness, and the 'future-proofing' of research and research services, can be instrumental in gaining high-level support. Without visible advocacy and prioritisation from the top, initiatives may struggle to affect policy, to gain traction, compete for resources, or overcome ingrained institutional practices.

See the [PID Value Proposition Resource](#) which outlines a number of value proposition scenarios that may apply to different institutions.

Policy

Institutional policy serves as a clear indicator of commitment and endorsement, signaling to researchers and support staff the strategic importance of PIDs. In the best cases, mandating or strongly encouraging the use of PIDs in policy can effectively drive adoption and establish PIDs as a standard practice in research workflows.

The true benefit of policy is realised when coupled with adequate resourcing for implementation and ongoing support. Institutional policy can guide the integration of PIDs into key research-relevant systems and workflows, aiding data flow, reliability, and reducing administrative burden on researchers and other staff. Within a comprehensive institutional approach, policy can trigger and shepherd strategies around systems, support and engagement, to grow the culture of PID use and more broadly realise the benefits.

Responsibility

Clearly defined roles and responsibilities for PID initiatives will increase the likelihood of success in efforts to progress your institution's PID maturity. Without a well-articulated framework of ownership, efforts towards PID adoption, implementation, support, and user experience can become fragmented, lack direction, and ultimately hinder progress. Identifying individuals and teams responsible for the different aspects of PID enabled services, workflows and systems provides a foundation for accountability, helping the institution to understand who is driving the work, providing support, and aiding a positive user experience.

Responsible individuals and teams should expect to benefit from PID initiatives and outcomes, so ideally they are roles within an institution that also have an interest in measuring and monitoring the progress and success. Defined responsibilities are essential for measuring PID maturity and improvement. Knowing which roles are accountable for PID implementation allows for targeted assessment of capabilities, and identification of areas where further development is needed. For example, understanding library responsibilities for PID minting and maintenance, compared with research administration or IT responsibilities, helps to pinpoint where expertise resides and where gaps may exist. Adding PID-related skills and experiences to position descriptions, professional development, and selection criteria can further embed responsibility within the institutional structure.

Resourcing

Tightly linked with clarity of responsibilities, the progress towards mature implementation and use of PIDs is subject to adequate human resourcing. Through all levels of maturity, institutions need to make resourcing and resource prioritising decisions according to the priority areas of impact.

The focus on resources may shift as the institution's maturity grows or as they observe certain benefits or challenges arising from PID implementations. For example, an institution may need to choose a focus among the following resource demands that would best progress their maturity from their current state. Few institutions will be able to commence all of these at once, but a sustainable investment in PIDs is likely to require resources in many of the following areas.

- Infrastructure and technical implementation: Integrating PIDs into existing systems such as repositories or research management systems, to realise the benefits of harvesting and using the metadata that powers PIDs
- Leadership and engagement: Personnel to champion PID adoption at an institutional, systems, and individual level, contributing to the development and implementation of PID-related policies
- Data management: Resource the integration of PIDs into data management policies and support services
- Communication, engagement, and user support: Building skills, resources and workflows to ensure researchers can effectively use and value PIDs
- Community engagement: Participation in national and international networks to learn from and contribute to best practice in supporting and using PIDs, and emerging issues.

Strategic allocation of resources across these key areas is essential not only for initial PID implementation but also for realising the institutional and sectoral benefits of the PID ecosystem.

User Experience

The benefits in research efficiency, productivity, and reduction in administrative burden envisioned by the National PID Strategy will be impacted by institutional maturity in supporting their users. Improving integration between systems, and consistency of experience across institutions – recognising that users may be affiliated with several institutions across their research career and sometimes concurrently – helps data about researchers, their effort and outputs, flow smoothly through the information landscape. Users will likely value PIDs more, and engage with those available for their use, when they can see how using them reduces time spent re-entering data.

The National PID Strategy's benefits will rely on effective user support, communications and system integrations, so a positive user experience is a high priority for achieving widespread and meaningful PID adoption within an institution. Managers play a crucial role in fostering this environment by championing user-centric approaches to implementation efforts. Intuitive workflows, clear guidance, and demonstrable time savings will make changes easier to embrace. Conversely, cumbersome processes, inconsistent system integrations, or a lack of adequate support will hinder progress towards greater maturity, regardless of the underlying PID technical capabilities. Ideally, much of the PIDs integration should occur invisibly or in the background, minimising the need for researchers to significantly alter their existing

workflows. Seamless PID integration in internal and external systems, facilitating data linkages and reuse, is key to a better user experience by eliminating repetitive manual data entry.

Keep in mind the experience to all users and the drivers and value to the wider research ecosystem, including researchers, funders and investors, institutions, facilities and infrastructure providers. As an example, ORCID researcher profiles and RAiD activity profiles go beyond institutional affiliation and will continue to promote researchers' work, achievements, collaborations, outputs, outcomes and ensure appropriate attribution. And PIDs can also ensure appropriate acknowledgement of institutions, investments and funders, other individual contributors, and aid in tracking outputs, outcomes and impact. With Australian institutions increasingly making verified information available via PIDs, significant time will be saved, but also trust in a researcher's profile will build over their career.

RAiD Capability Maturity

Due its relationship with all other identifiers, RAiD maturity requires a special mention. If an organisation's context and business drivers have prioritised RAiD, the maturity of and prioritisation of other identifiers should be a consideration. In fact, RAiD can drive the development of related PIDs that are important to realising benefits. RAiDs interlink a number of trusted identifiers in order to accurately represent the history and contributions to research activities from individuals, institutions, funders, facilities and other research inputs. Furthermore, RAiDs connect the research activity context with the activity's outputs and other outcomes, helping to identify impact. Outputs could include traditional academic outputs such as journal publications and books, but also reports, resources, data, other research artefacts, and even subsequent activities such as further work or funding.

Capability Maturity Matrix

<input type="checkbox"/> Maturity Level <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Maturity Area <input type="checkbox"/>	Beginner	Intermediate	Advanced
Roles & Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Senior leadership (VC, DVCR, PVC level, Directors, C-suite) encouragement and endorsement of the 5 national priority PIDs has been sought, in the context of the organisation's business drivers. (See Value Proposition Resource including scenarios, and the 5 national priority PIDs) Divisional or team leadership and responsibility is defined and clear for PID advocacy, implementation, and/or support. There is a nominated role/person at the institution who is the ORCID admin contact, and is responsible for monitoring the institution's RORs. A role or unit within the organisation has the authority and permission (via appropriate institutional agreements, terms and accounts) to commence minting PIDs that align with business drivers, for example Datacite DOIs for outputs, funding, instruments, samples. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Divisional or team leadership and responsibility for PID advocacy and researcher support is clear to users and organisational leads. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The institution is actively attending, participating and being represented in national PID strategy forums and community events, to better leverage and advise national advancements, services and to benefit from cross-institutional knowledge transfer.
Governance & Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PID creation, use and adoption is encouraged by policy, and this is based on the organisation's business drivers. (See Value Proposition Resource including scenarios, and the 5 national priority PIDs) There is policy expecting all research staff and students to have and have registered an ORCID. (e.g. effectively that having ORCID is the default, unless opting-out) There are guidelines about ORCID visibility settings: setting "everyone" is recommended, but at least setting "trusted parties" is expected. This is required to maximise PID efficiency benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Procedures now operationalise relevant policies, designed to encourage PID creation and use. Priorities can be based on the organisation's business drivers. (e.g. Information Management, Research Data Management, Open Access, Intellectual Property policies) Business subject matter experts advocate for maturity of PID use in development and review of relevant policy. (e.g. Information Management, Research Data Management, Open Access, Intellectual Property policies) PID adoption is benchmarked, both use & quality, in line with business priorities. There are plans to benchmark regularly. Clear Information Management and Governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisational reporting or benchmarking engages with PID-driven indicators and initiatives. (e.g. Leiden Ranking, Altmetric, RLA)

		<p>exists regarding researcher profile information, the point-of-truth system, and their integration with ORCID.</p>	
<p>Communication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of the use and importance of PIDs is part of active outreach to researchers (including the org's business drivers). • Institutional messaging includes... <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ the importance of capturing and sharing accurate metadata openly, and the important role PIDs play in doing this (e.g. by setting ORCID to be visible to everyone); and ◦ minting and capturing PIDs in integrated systems enables the flow of verified information ... These messages should be embedded in research support and outreach • Researchers can find institutional guidance on how to mint or use DOIs, either done online, or self-service, or dependent on open community tools like Zenodo/ figshare.com. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs and/or links are routinely available on public-facing and internal systems for documenting research outputs. • Institutional messaging includes... <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ the need for quality institutional information and the processes this supports (e.g. as supported by ORCID records) ◦ in particular, how PID data supports external reporting requirements, and how this data might support internal research performance reporting, evaluation reporting, and business intelligence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational communications draw upon PID-enabled analytics for researcher support, promotion of achievements, or celebrating wins. (e.g. additional support provided to highly cited/visible researchers; public facing communications and external engagement etc.)
<p>User Experience</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-boarding processes exist where all academics and research students are guided to create or provide an ORCID (opting-out only by exception), and all authenticated ORCIDs are captured in enterprise system(s). https://info.orcid.org/documentation/workflows/employment-workflow/ • Researchers and institutions use PIDs in capturing information for grant application systems and processes, rather than reentry of descriptive metadata. This can later aid in linking previous/related grants, outputs, organisations, people, and projects. • Workflow improvements are being actively considered by identifying steps that could benefit, especially those reducing re-keying efforts and sourcing information from trusted sources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs are encouraged in in-house training and outreach for researchers and research students including important messages (see Communications maturity). • Outreach, support and/or processes target academics and research students who have not integrated their ORCID with the required admin system(s), e.g. internal reports sent to supervisors; integrated into PDF review; or missing ORCIDs result in targeted offers of support • Support pathways or key contacts for PID minting and usage advice can be easily found by researchers and research students. • Supported PID minting requests should result in timely or where possible immediate PIDs, as slow request processing will discourage uptake and use. • Flow of research management and bibliographic information between reporting systems is facilitated or aided by PIDs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is evidence that researchers are routinely using their ORCID when submitting outputs to publishers or publishing outputs on non-institutionally managed repositories. • Reusing PIDs and associated information to reduce administration is routine. • Using PIDs and associated information to reduce the reporting burden is routine.

<p>Resourcing & Skills</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Divisional or team responsibilities for PID leadership, implementation, support, and/or advocacy is defined and clear. • PIDs awareness, implementation and strategy are included in training, onboarding, developing engagement, and for research support professionals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Divisional or team leadership and responsibility is resourced and PID implementation and support is being prioritised. • PID support and/or advocacy is being resourced as part of relevant professional staff roles. • Engagement and research support professionals participate in events coordinated by PID communities. • ORCID and Datacite Consortium member institutions should have taken advantage of available national consultation advice, national skills, (AAF, ARDC) and networking opportunities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research support professionals, and/or organisational leaders are active in and contribute to PID community coordinated events.
<p>Workflow</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are institutional plans to follow the ORCID Integration Best Practices. https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-best-practices/ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting on and review of researchers still needing to register ORCIDs is occurring. And operationally, there should be processes to reach out to these researchers, channeling them into registration workflows and support (or recognition of opt-out justification). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaps in integrated workflows are being identified and acted on, for the use of and movement of PIDs and associated information.
<p>Implementation Core Systems & Technology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only authenticated ORCID IDs are collected, for researchers & research students. https://info.orcid.org/documentation/workflows/employment-workflow/ • Researcher profile sites/pages display ORCIDs for researchers. • Institutional (research) repositories display ORCIDs for researchers and these are available via the repository API. • Systems have the ability to capture and deliver minimum mandatory DOI metadata elements (as required by Datacite or Crossref) and a landing page to enable a DOI minting workflow. • Systems have the ability to deliver minimum ORCID metadata to ORCID to assert affiliation as described on ORCID technical schema. (organisational ID, name, country, start date of researcher) • DOIs are actively encouraged for all forms of research output. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems (e.g. CRIS, RIMS, IR) write verified information to researchers' ORCIDs including employment affiliation, education & qualification affiliation, funding, works, website links to online profiles. https://info.orcid.org/research-information-systems • Specifically, when researcher outputs are captured or reported, and verified, this is appropriately written to the researchers' ORCIDs . • DOIs for outputs are being minted by the institution, especially for non-publisher outputs, which must resolve to an appropriate web page. (e.g. grey literature such as reports, discussion papers, online resources, other research artefacts such as creative works, performance, datasets) • ORCID and related data are collected and shared with automation support across more than one system. • Institutional repository systems follow best practice workflows. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDs are considered as part of tools/ systems procurement processes and/or core system integration processes. • When a researcher receives or changes funding information (including verified funder or facility grants), this is appropriately written to the researcher's ORCID. • DOIs for outputs, grants and instruments are being actively and systematically minted. • Institutional research repositories display ORCIDs and PIDs for all contributors, including external contributors, and these are available via the repository API.

		<p>https://info.orcid.org/repository-systems/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When a researcher joins or leaves the institution, an updated affiliation is written to the ORCID's employment, education or qualification information, including start and end date. 	
<p>Reporting & benchmarking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> With increasing numbers of ORCID's and other PIDs having linked affiliations to the institution (via ROR), research outputs and outcomes will become increasingly and more accurately associated with the institution. Uptake in PIDs within institutional repositories will lead to more visible and traceable outputs. These will begin to benefit institutional performance measurement and impact tracking. (see the Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Benchmarking Toolkit - Final Report https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.29281667) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For internal performance and evaluation reporting, PIDs are being used (either directly, or indirectly via RMS/RIMS information collecting workflows) to ensure the highest quality of, highest coverage of, and most up-to-date information on academic activities, outputs and achievements. For administrative reporting purposes, PIDs are used to confirm missing outputs for the institution's research publication/outputs collection (ORCID's, DOIs, in some cases outputs targeted with organisation ROR), required of Universities as evidence for TEQSA and for ARC as evidence for Quality of Research. (see TEQSA acceptable evidence for Quality of Research. https://www.teqsa.gov.au/guides-resources/resources/guidance-notes/guidance-note-research-requirements-australian-universities) For administrative reporting purposes PIDs are used to confirm missing funding for the institution's research income collection (ORCID's, and in some cases targeted with ROR and grant DOIs), required of Universities for the Department of Education HERDC. This may also support better reporting against the ABS HERD reporting. (see HERDC https://www.education.gov.au/research-block-grants/higher-education-research-data-collection ; and ABS HERD https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/industry/technology-and-innovation/research-and-experimental-development-higher-education-organisations-australia/2022) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal reporting systems are able to recognise important PIDs, which may be created or registered internally (information in internal systems), or may be created or registered externally by researchers, collaborators, funders etc. Internal reporting systems are able to use both internal and external (PID) information sources. (e.g. for performance, impact, analytics)

<p>Facilities & Instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A role or unit within the organisation has the authority and permission (via appropriate institutional agreements, terms and accounts) to commence minting Datacite DOIs for facilities and instruments, and potentially related PIDs such as reference datasets, output datasets. • Facilities, instrument owners, or administrators are able to enter appropriate metadata for DOIs for each instrument via a PID ready platform that can mint and maintain Datacite DOIs. • Consideration is given to where within an institution it is crucial to track the usage or potential demand on instruments, such as ethics or DMP's allow association with instrument DOI. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is clear information management or governance regarding instruments and a point-of- truth information management system. (e.g. database, spreadsheet, web content platform, commercial system) • A system is being actively used to mint and maintain the Datacite DOI's for instruments across the institution, including ensuring the DOI resolves to an appropriate web page. • Systems have the ability to associate calibration data, input data, and output data with instrument DOI. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instrument PID metadata is able to be harvested by other systems for re-use. • Platform booking processes capture ORCID, ROR, and Grant/Project IDs. • Instrument PIDs are being cited in publications by authors and/or publisher metadata.
<p>RAiD Capability Maturity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the context of the organisation's business drivers, identify the importance of RAiD to those drivers, and those responsible for PID advocacy, implementation, and/or support (see Governance above) should begin developing a plan. • Those responsible for developing a RAiD plan should leverage national RAiD Product Management support. • Maturity of a range of other PIDs should be assessed, as RAiD can be a catalyst for the development of related PIDs important to the local context and drivers. • Systems have the ability to capture RAiDs associated with research outputs and other artefacts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review the maturity and accuracy of PIDs in core systems and their ability to identify: internal and external individuals, partner institutions, facilities, funding and funders, outputs (e.g. publications, reports, resources, data, other research artefacts), and potentially crucial research inputs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An institutional operational policy and process must exist that identifies or registers research activities (some or all might be externally visible RAiDs) and captures basic metadata for these, i.e. title; dates; description; contributor CIs, PIs, co-Is; funding & funders; lead & partner organisations; website URL. (see RAiD core metadata https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/core.html#overview) • Institutional processes or touch-points exist that can capture or identify additional complexity in linking related research activities and related funding together, e.g. preceding, subsequent or related projects. (see relatedRAiD types https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedRAiDs.html#relatedraid-type) • Association of research outputs with a research activity is streamlined. (see relatedRAiD types) • Institutional processes or touch-points exist that can capture or identify additional complexity in research activity inputs, beyond grants, e.g. facility access grants, significant instruments,

			<p>significant datasets, databanks or other resource usage. (see RAID relatedObject type https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedObjects.html#relatedobject-type)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional processes or touch-points exist that can capture or identify additional complexity in research activity contributors, e.g. contractor organisations, facility organisations, other research & non-research organisations, consultants & other individual contributors (see RAID org roles & contributor roles https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/organisations.html#organisation-role https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/contributors.html#contributor-role)
--	--	--	--

Important References

- Australian PID Strategy Institutions Stakeholder Group, “PID Value Proposition Resource”. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18383260>
- Australian PID Strategy Institutions Stakeholder Group, “PIDs Implementation Guide”. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18383351>
- Australian Access Federation, “ORCID Maturity Assessment Criteria”, accessed 2025. https://docs.google.com/document/d/1V5hk6nX_vd-534eQCGiDDU8y4tDdxWq0/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=105418465812717135517&rtpof=true&sd=true
- Macquarie University, “Research Authorship Policy” (example, mandated ORCIDs for all researchers), released 2023, accessed 2025. <https://policies.mq.edu.au/document/view.php?id=378>
- Josh Brown et. al. “Incentives to Invest in Identifiers: A cost-benefit analysis of persistent identifiers in Australian research systems”, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7100577>
 - 2 case studies included: Case study 1 - ORCID and Crossref integration in ARC’s RMS system for grant applications; Case study 2 - The use of PIDs at TERN.
- McCafferty, S., Poger, D., Yvette, W., Seal, C., Burgess, R., & Kenna, E. (2023). “Best Practices: PIDs for Instruments (1.0)”, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7759201>
 - 5 case studies included: University of New South Wales; University of Queensland; CSIRO; University of Auckland; Microscopy Australia.
- Schnieders, K., Mierz, S., Boccalini, S., Meyer zu Westerhausen, W., Hauschke, C., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., & Schulze, S. (2022). “ORCID coverage in research institutions—Readiness for partially automated research reporting”. *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, 7, 1010504. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2022.1010504>
- CODATA Data Science Journal, “20 Years of Persistent Identifiers: Applications and Future Directions”, collection launched 2017. <https://datascience.codata.org/collections/20-years-of-persistent-identifiers-applications-and-future-directions>
- Digital Science, Simon Porter et. al. “Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Benchmarking Toolkit – Final Report”, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.29281667.v3>